

Free Trade Zones in Jordan

Bashar H. Malkawi*

Introduction

Most developing countries have begun to shift from import-substitution to export-looking trade policies.¹ One dimension of this has been the establishment of free trade zones (FTZs) for such economic activity as export promotion or industrial development.² It is estimated that, by 1975, there were seventy-nine FTZs spread out in twenty-five countries and that one hundred thirty-five countries hosted three thousand five hundred FTZs.³ The rapid proliferation of these zones, however, was not limited to developing countries. Some of the richest countries host FTZs, like Australia, Singapore, the United States, Italy, Ireland, Spain and other European countries.⁴

These FTZs are considered as one of the government's development tools to promote its exports. The purpose of these areas is to attract foreign capital, foreign technology, encourage technology diffusion, and economic development and managerial skills.⁵ However, the concept of FTZs has been criticized on a number of

* Bashar H. Malkawi is Professor of Law, University of Sharjah, UAE. He holds S.J.D in Law from American University, Washington College of Law and LL.M in International Trade & Business Law from the University of Arizona.

¹ See Ashok Kundra, *The Performance of India's Export Zones: A Comparison with the Chinese Approach* 24 (2000).

² See John R. McIntyre, Rajneesh Narula & Len J. Trevino, *The Role of Export Processing Zones for the Host Countries and Multinationals: A Mutually Beneficial Relationship?* X:4 *The Int'l Trade J.* 435, 440 (1996) (the first two zones established in developing countries were Mayaguez, Puerto Rico (1962) and Kandla, India (1965)).

³ See WORLD BANK, *SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES: PROGRESS, EMERGING CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS* 5 (Thomas Farole & Gokhan Akinci, eds., 2011), available at <<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/2011/01/14813550/special-economic-zones-progress-emerging-challenges-future-directions>>.

⁴ See Gordon H. Hanson, *Should Countries Promote Foreign Direct Investment* 9 (2001), available at <<http://dspace.cigilibrary.org/jspui/bitstream/123456789/21535/1/Should%20Countries%20Promote%20Foreign%20Direct%20Investment.pdf?1>>.

⁵ One of the main benefits of establishing free economic zones is the relocation of production from developed to developing countries with the hope of exploiting the low cost of labor. They also play an important part in the evolution of the new international division of labor. Another rationale for free

grounds. Determining the rules applicable to these zones is challenging, for the law of the World Trade Organization (WTO) does not regulate them. Indeed, there is neither a standardized definition of nor a standardized model for FTZs. Their nomenclature also varies greatly. Some use the terms free trade zones, special economic zones, maquiladoras, free trade zones, free export zones, special economic zones, economic and technological development zones, export-oriented units, or foreign trade zone as synonyms.⁶ Some distinguish between these terms.⁷ Others adopt the term export processing zone as a general expression that covers all its different variations.⁸

Nevertheless, the thrust of criticism is that FTZs have limited success in the development of developing countries economies. First, most zones employ mainly low skilled workers with lax labor codes and health and safety standards.⁹ One of their supposed advantages, the generation of employment through the attraction of foreign firms, has its limitations, in terms of the type of jobs generated and the long-term sustainability of these jobs.¹⁰ As far as zone-host economy backward linkages are concerned, there is normally very little technology transfer from FTZs to the host

zones is to generate foreign exchange needed for debt servicing. Another impact on domestic firms results from the close contact with foreign firms. This leads to intra-firm growth and domestic sub-contracting. *Id.* at 441-452. See also David Kelly, A Life of One's Own: Individual Rights and the Welfare State 1-8, in P. Alston, R. Goodman, H. J. Steiner, *International Human Rights in Context* (3rd ed., 2007) ([t]he economic and technological development of a society affects the degree to which it can provide welfare rights to its members).

⁶ The author opts to use the term free trade zones throughout the paper as used by in the Revised Kyoto Convention of the World Customs Organization (WCO). See Annex D of the International Convention on the Harmonization and Simplification of Customs, available at <<http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/cefact/recommendations/kyoto/welcome.htm>>.

⁷ See FIAS, *Special Economic Zones: Performance, Lessons Learned, and Implications for Zone Development* 9 (2008), available at <[http://www.ifc.org/ifcext/fias.nsf/AttachmentsByTitle/SEZpaperdiscussion/\\$FILE/SEZs+report_April2008.pdf](http://www.ifc.org/ifcext/fias.nsf/AttachmentsByTitle/SEZpaperdiscussion/$FILE/SEZs+report_April2008.pdf)>.

⁸ See International Labor Organization, *Resource Guide on Export Processing Zones* (2007), available at <<http://www.ilo.org/public/english/support/lib/resource/subject/epz.htm>>.

⁹ See Bernard M. Hoekman and Michel M. Kostecki, *The Political Economy of the World Trading System* 629 (2009).

¹⁰ See McIntyre, Narula and Trevino, *supra* note 1, at 441-452.

country.¹¹ The value of tax incentives granted to firms operating in FTZs is also debatable.¹² Therefore, the revenue forgone and social cost incurred in establishing FTZs could be higher than actual benefits.

I. The FTZ Statute of Jordan

FTZs in Jordan are governed by the Free Zone Corporation that manages economic, trade, and industrial affairs in the zones.¹³ The Free Zones Corporation Law rests responsibility for the construction of buildings and the provision of infrastructure and services upon the Free Zone Corporation. To establish a FTZ, the Free Zones Corporation may declare any area as a FTZ.¹⁴ Such an announcement specifies scope of activities to be carried out in the zone concerned.¹⁵ Thus, the law allows for restrictions in terms of types of activities that can be carried out in the zone. In addition to storage and manufacture of goods, the Free Zones Corporation Law allows economic operators in the zones to provide services as well.¹⁶ Special conditions in terms of impact on environment need to be attached to a licensed

¹¹ See Nicola A. Virgill, *Export Processing Zones: Tools of Development or Reform Delay?* 28-30, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, George Mason University (2009).

¹² See Susan Tiefenbrun, *U.S. Foreign Trade Zones, Tax-Free Trade Zones of the World, and their Impact on the U.S. Economy*, 12 *J. Int'l Bus. & L.* 149, 155, 199 (2013) (Income on profits in the United States Foreign Trade Zones is not exempt from federal income, capital dividend, royalty, interest, and other passive income taxes).

¹³ The Free Zone Corporation Board is composed of the Minister of Finance as chairman, the director general of the Free Zone Corporation, and members from the MIT, Ministry of Finance/Customs Service, Ministry of Transportation, and the Central Bank. With regards to the governance of free zones there are three types: a free zone in which management of investment is vested into the Corporation, a free zone in which a private company is responsible for its administration subject to the Corporation's regulations, and a free zone in which it is run by private-public companies. See Free Zones Corporation Law No. 32 of 1984, Official Gazette No. 3280 (Dec. 16, 1984), as amended by Provisional Law No. 41 of 2003, art. 4.2 & 6, Official Gazette No. 4598 (May. 15, 2003).

¹⁴ *Id.* art. 4.a. The free zones which have been established are divided into public and private free zones. There are several public FTZs such as Zarqa free zone, Sahab free zone, and Al-Karak free zone established in 2001. In addition to these public free zones, there are many private free zones. For example, Jordan-Indo Chemicals Company, Hejazi & Gousheh Company, Trans-Jordan Livestock Company, and FTZs at Jordanian airports.

¹⁵ *Id.* art. 4.f.

¹⁶ *Id.* art. 2.

enterprise in a free zone.¹⁷ Other conditions include development, free zone-domestic market ties, and labor skills.¹⁸

The Free Zones Corporation Law offers enterprises generous packages consisting of an array of economic incentives. Enterprises are exempted from paying income tax on profits.¹⁹ They are permitted repatriation of investment or profits attributable to investments they make. Imports into a FTZ are not to be subjected to tariffs and other types of taxes.²⁰ The Free Zones Corporation Law is silent on the legal process for the settlement of disputes between a licensed enterprise and the Free Zones Corporation or between two or more licensed enterprises within a FTZ.

II. Export Subsidies

Export subsidies have always been a prominent and disputed matter.²¹ On the one hand, some scholars stand for adoption of export subsidies especially by developing countries.²² These scholars assert that "[e]conomic theory suggests ... that subsidies are not as trade distorting as other trade instruments (like, for example, quantitative restrictions or tariffs) which affect two margins (both the producer's and the consumer's)," whereas "subsidies affect one margin only (the producer's)".²³ On the other hand, it can be argued that export subsidisation distorts free trade; "such subsidies cut into the exports of other countries that have a natural comparative advantage in those products, and so distort the world's allocation of resources".²⁴

¹⁷ *Id.* art. 4.g. However, the language as written does not permit challenges by environmental groups regarding the potential impact of increased economic activity as a result of the establishment of a free zone. Absurdly, there is no specific provision on workers' rights.

¹⁸ *Id.* art. 13.b.

¹⁹ *Id.* art. 13.d.

²⁰ *Id.*

²¹ See Wentong Zheng, *Counting Once, Counting Twice: The Precarious State of Subsidy Regulation*, 49 STAN. J INT'L L. 427, 432 (2013).

²² See Ha-Joon Chang, *Why Developing Countries Need Tariffs — How WTO NAMA Negotiations Could Deny Developing Countries' Right to a Future* 14-16 (November 2005).

²³ See Mitsuo Matsushita, Thomas J. Schoenbaum, and Petros C. Mavroidis, *THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION: LAW, PRACTICE, AND POLICY* 332 (2006).

²⁴ See Douglas A. Irwin, *FREE TRADE UNDER FIRE* 147 (2009).

Despite these academic disputes, it is clear, with respect to export subsidies, that, since the negotiations that resulted in the adoption of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade of 1947 (GATT 1947),²⁵ the view that they must be avoided is prevalent not only in international instruments, such as the GATT and the SCM Agreement, but also in the dispute settlement of the WTO.²⁶

Export subsidies are presumed under the WTO Agreement to cause negative trade effects.²⁷ Therefore, to analyze whether the exemption from import duties on goods entering FTZs is consistent with Art. 3.1(a) of the SCM Agreement, it is sufficient to determine whether this exemption falls within the definition of "export subsidies" as included in the SCM Agreement which applies to trade in goods only. There is no need to prove adverse effects on other members since the damage, in a case where recourse to a prohibited subsidy is being made, is not the trade effects caused, but rather the act of subsidization itself.²⁸

²⁵ In the Uruguay Round Final Act, the GATT is referred to as the GATT 1947 throughout and is furthermore incorporated, with important exceptions, into the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade 1994. See Final Act Embodying the Results of the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations, Dec. 15, 1993, Part II, ann. 1A, art. XVI, GATT Doc. No. MTN/FA, U.S.T., 33 I.L.M. 1130, 1145 (1994). In conformity with the Final Act's usage, the author will refer to the GATT as the GATT 1947 where appropriate, but will also retain the original designation of GATT when referring to the multilateral trading system as it has evolved under the GATT 1947 obligations.

²⁶ See, for instance, *Canada – Measures Affecting the Export of Civilian Aircraft (Canada – Aircraft)*, WT/DS/70/R 14 April 1999, para. 9.119.

²⁷ See Marc Bacchetta and Marion Jansen, *Adjusting to Trade Liberalization: The Role of Policy, Institutions and WTO Disciplines*. WTO Special Studies No. 7, 60 (2003), available at <http://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/special_study_7_e.pdf>.

²⁸ See Mitsuo Matsushita, Thomas J. Schoenbaum, and Petros C. Mavroidis *supra* note 25, at 369.